

First Temple (Jerusalem)

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The First Temple, sometimes called "Solomon's Temple," was likely built at some point in the 10th century BCE. The conventional dating for Solomon's reign is roughly 970-930 BCE and the Temple was completed at some point in the middle of the 10th century BCE, around 959. The Hebrew Bible contains descriptions of the temple, including an account of its destruction by the Babylonian king Nebuchadnezzar II in 587 BCE. Today, archaeologists are unable to conduct work on the site (Temple Mount), as the al-Aqsa Mosque currently sits there. Given that, details must be reconstructed through other historical sources. The Hebrew Bible describes the Temple as having three sections: an outer porch, a sanctuary, and an innermost shrine (the holy of holies). Additionally, Bronze age "long-room" temples from nearby Phoenician sites have similar layouts and features, which gives insight to what the First Temple may have looked like.

Date Range: 960 BCE - 587 BCE

Region: Temple Mount

Region tags: Israel, Jerusalem

Temple Mount in Jerusalem, where the First Temple stood before it was destroyed in 587 BCE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Joseph L. Trafton, "Temple, Jerusalem," in *The Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary*, Volume 6: Si-z, ed. David Noel Freedman (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1992), 350-68.
- Source 1: Katharina Galor and Hanswulf Bloedhorn, *The Archaeology of Jerusalem: From the Origins to the Ottomans* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2013).
- Source 1: Texts from the Hebrew Bible: 2 Chronicles 2-7; 1 Kings 4-8
- Source 1: Alan Balfour, *Solomon's Temple : Myth, Conflict, and Faith* (Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2012)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://bibleodyssey.org/places/main-articles/first-temple/>

– Source 1 Description: "First Temple" (Bible Odyssey)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: The texts in 1 Kings 6 and 2 Chronicles 4 describes courtyards that are sectioned off with rows of stone. There was also a storage building next to the temple.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Probably; 1 Kings 6:29-30 seem to indicate that there were walls around the temple.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the text in 2 Chronicles 4 suggests that there was a large altar and basin outside of the temple.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A group of features:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: The priests would offer sacrifices and maintain the temple on behalf of

the rest of the Israelites.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: It is assumed that the temple was burned, given that textual sources describe the burning of the city when the temple was destroyed. Archaeological evidence has neither confirmed nor denied this.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: No.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Yahweh

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The construction of the temple is ascribed to the Israelite king Solomon.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Slaves

– Corvee labourers

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by high god

Notes: 1 Chronicles 28:10 suggests that Yahweh chose Solomon to build the temple. In 1 Kings 6, Yahweh promises to bless Solomon if he builds the temple and obeys his commands.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: However, 1 Kings 5 claims that Solomon purchased materials and labor from King Hiram of Tyre.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 250

Notes: 1 Kings 6:2 says the temple was 60 cubits long and 20 cubits wide, which may be around 27m x 9m depending on the exact value of a cubit.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 13.5

Notes: 1 Kings 6:2 says the temple was 30 cubits high, which may be around 13.5m depending on the exact value of a cubit.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: 1 Kings 5 suggests that the wood used in the temple was cedar from Lebanon

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Notes: However, 1 Kings 6 describes how certain objects were overlaid with gold for decorative purposes.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and

inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For example, 1 Kings 6 describes a pair of cherubim carved from olive wood.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For example, 1 Kings 7 describes a large basin called the "Molten Sea" that is held up by statues of twelve bulls

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: However, most of it is inside the temple, which would non-priests would not have seen.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: In the Hebrew Bible in general, Yahweh is given anthropomorphic features (hands, nose, eyes, etc.). However, Yahweh is described as a pillar of smoke when he resides in the temple or tabernacle.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Presumably wine.

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Grain, oil, flour

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Cattle, ram, sheep, certain birds

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The field remains uncertain as to the status and function of the so-called "cult prostitute" (zonah, qedeshah).

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ritual participants would wash themselves, but the purposes seems to be more about ritual/symbolic purity than hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Cattle, ram, sheep, certain birds

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 1 Kings 15:15 mentions one king bringing in vessels of silver and gold for the temple.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 1 Chronicles 26:27 indicates that plunder from battle was donated to the temple for its maintenance. However, we do not have texts that indicate what kind of maintenance may have happened, how regularly it may have occurred, or who was in charge of it.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Texts like 1 Chronicles 9 indicate that certain clans had dedicated roles that kept the temple functioning. For example, the Kohathites seemed to be in charge of preparing the showbread each week.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably. Texts like Deuteronomy 31:10-11 seem to instruct as much, but textual records do not record such pilgrimages.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably. For example, Exodus 34:18-23 instructs the Israelites to appear before Yahweh each year to celebrate the Feast of Unleavened bread. However, textual records do not record such festivals.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: For example, people would present offerings for the deity.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: The textual evidence doesn't say.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: The textual evidence doesn't say.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: For example, in 2 Kings 23, King Josiah rids the temple of non-Yahwistic practices that seemed to have crept in.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It seems that incense was burned, but it is unclear if anything intoxicating was burned.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male priests.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Israelite

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: They are priests

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: There was a high priest; the rest of the priests seem to be divided and assigned to different temple duties, but it is unclear if a hierarchy was present in these duties.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: Only the high priest could enter the innermost part of the sanctuary (the holy of holies).

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not; the texts suggest that Levites had their own towns to live in (priests were from the tribe of Levi)

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: The limited textual evidence suggests that priests were organized into different groups and were responsible for various tasks that ensured that the workings of the temple would continue.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: Probably; Leviticus 27, for example, describes the dedication of houses, temple, people, etc. made to the temple, but it is unclear how the temple may have controlled those resources.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The texts do not indicate either way.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temple was destroyed and its likely site remains inaccessible to archaeologists to this day.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: 1 Kings 4-8 and 2 Chronicles 2-7.

- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: First Temple (Jerusalem), Mendelsohn, I.. "On Corvée Labor in Ancient Canaan and Israel". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 167 (1962): 31-35.

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